

Tool Artifact for “Variability Fault Localization by Abstract Interpretation and its Application to SPL Repair”

Aleksandar S. Dimovski¹

Mother Teresa University, st. Mirche Acev nr. 4, 1000 Skopje, North Macedonia
`aleksandar.dimovski@unt.edu.mk`

Abstract. In this work, we describe the installation, usage, and evaluation results of the tool, denoted `SPLFaultLoc`, introduced by the paper “Variability Fault Localization by Abstract Interpretation and its Application to SPL Repair”. We provide step-by-step instructions on how to download, run, and compare the tool’s outputs to outputs described in the paper. The tool is a research prototype SPL fault localizer for analyzing program families (SPLs) in C using abstract interpretation. It uses an iterative refinement sequence of backward-forward lifted abstract analyses to compute lifted error invariants, which are used for feature- and statement-wise semantic slicing of buggy SPLs that removes the statements irrelevant for assertion violation. Moreover, we have integrated our `SPLFaultLoc` with the `SPLAllRepair` tool to design an efficient SPL repair algorithm that repeatedly mutates expressions in the statement identified as relevant for the bug until a correct SPL is found.

1 Introduction

This work summarises the evaluation results reported by the paper “Variability Fault Localization by Abstract Interpretation and its Application to SPL Repair”. It applies for: **Artifact Evaluated - Functional** and **Artifact Available** Badges at SLE AE 2025. To evaluate the performances of the variability fault localization algorithm, we compare three tools:

- `SPLFaultLoc` — Variability Fault Localization that uses an iterative refinement sequence of backward-forward lifted analyses, which is based on the polyhedra domain from the APRON library [6], the BDDAPRON library [5], and the Z3 SMT solver [1].
- `SPLFaultLoc_Single` — Variability Fault Localization that uses a single backward lifted analysis, which is based on the polyhedra domain from the APRON library [6] and the BDDAPRON library [5].
- `Brute-Force` — Variability Fault Localization that uses a preprocessor to generate all variants of a program family and then applies the single-program fault localization tool `FAULTLOC` [2] to each individual variant one by one.

To evaluate the performances of the newly designed SPL repair algorithm, we compare two tools:

- `SPL(FaultLoc+AllRepair)` — SPL repair that combines our `SPLFaultLoc` and the `SPLAllRepair` tool [3], which uses mutations of levels 1 and 2.
- `SPLAllRepair` — SPL repair [3] with no variability fault localization integrated into it, which uses mutations of levels 1 and 2.

2 Downloading

2.1 VM

The URL of the tool artifact is available from Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/uploads/13957325>

The files inside this folder are:

- `xubuntu.7z.001` (md5:1649dd3816b804d828fbbf5f1bbd94b5)
- `xubuntu.7z.002` (md5:1e32b9b4528f9e8e32b0cf61155fa10e)
- `SPLFaultLoc.tar.gz` (md5:ae0e07d33892a1608bfc85db10eba7a9)
- `HowToInstall.txt` (md5:520ba970578d31525bb086a669ac7512)
- `Intructions.txt` (md5:b0cdeb867397a53910950f4f715fc799)
- `ExperimentalResultsTable1.txt` (md5:d79ee1fe4911e4de1fa3f1f55d043008)
- `ExperimentalResultsTable2.txt` (md5:4524b07c7c7bd3863696fff1f527d9ae)
- `tool-doc.pdf`

Once you download all files, use 7Zip to restore VM image “`xubuntu.ova`”. The virtual machine containing the tool installed and ready to use is “`user`”: `tool`, “`password`”: `tool`.

2.2 tar.gz file

To install the tool by yourself, download the file: `SPLFaultLoc.tar.gz` from the Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/uploads/13957325>.

* Untar the given file:

```
tar -xvf SPLFaultLoc.tar.gz
```

* Enter the folder that contains the tools

```
cd SPLFaultLoc
```

* For step-by-step installation of the tools follow:

```
HowToInstall.txt
```

* Note that you have to install Ocaml, Apron, BDDApron, Z3, and Python3.

3 Running Experiments

* For step-by-step execution of all test cases of the tools follow:

```
Instructions.txt
```

We now present all instructions that need to be run in order to generate all data from Table 1 and Table 2 in the companion paper [4].

3.1 Table 1

* Enter the folder that contains the tool

```
cd SPLFaultLoc
```

* If you want to recompile the tool, delete “Main.native” file and “_build” folder, and use the following two commands:

```
eval $(opam config env)
```

```
ocamlbuild Main.native -use-ocamlfind -use-menhir
```

```
-pkgs 'bddapron,apron,gmp,oUnit,zarith' -I utils -I banal -I domains
```

```
-I frontend -I main -libs boxMPQ,octD,polkaMPQ,str,zarith,bddapron
```

To run SPLFaultLoc, SPLFaultLoc_Single, and Brute-Force on the examples from the paper [4] (see Table 1), we write the following commands.

SPLFaultLoc

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -domain polyhedra benchmarks/intro.c
```

Note: the option “-full” means that we use the full iterated sequence of backward-forward abstract analyses; and the option “-domain polyhedra” specifies that the abstract domain used is Polyhedra.

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -domain polyhedra benchmarks/intro-b.c
```

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -domain polyhedra benchmarks/cond.c
```

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -domain polyhedra benchmarks/cond-b.c
```

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -domain polyhedra benchmarks/while.c
```

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -domain polyhedra benchmarks/easy2-1.c
```

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -domain polyhedra benchmarks/Mysore-1.c
```

SPLFaultLoc_Single

```
$ time ./Main.native -single -domain polyhedra benchmarks/intro.c
```

Note: the option “-single” means that we use the single backward abstract analysis.

```
$ time ./Main.native -single -domain polyhedra benchmarks/intro-b.c
```

```
$ time ./Main.native -single -domain polyhedra benchmarks/cond.c
```

```
$ time ./Main.native -single -domain polyhedra benchmarks/cond-b.c
```

```
$ time ./Main.native -single -domain polyhedra benchmarks/while.c
```

```
$ time ./Main.native -single -domain polyhedra benchmarks/easy2-1.c
$ time ./Main.native -single -domain polyhedra benchmarks/Mysore-1.c
```

Brute-Force

```
$ time ./Main.native -bf -domain polyhedra benchmarks/intro
Note: the option “-bf” means that we handle all variants of the given SPL
“intro.c” (that are located in the folder “intro”) independently one by one in
a brute-force manner.
$ time ./Main.native -bf -domain polyhedra benchmarks/intro-b
$ time ./Main.native -bf -domain polyhedra benchmarks/cond
$ time ./Main.native -bf -domain polyhedra benchmarks/cond-b
$ time ./Main.native -bf -domain polyhedra benchmarks/while
$ time ./Main.native -bf -domain polyhedra benchmarks/easy2-1
$ time ./Main.native -bf -domain polyhedra benchmarks/Mysore-1
```

3.2 Table 2

To run $SPL(\text{FaultLoc}+\text{AllRepair})_1$, $SPL\text{AllRepair}_1$, $SPL(\text{FaultLoc}+\text{AllRepair})_2$ and $SPL\text{AllRepair}_2$ on the examples from the paper [4] (see Table 2), we write the following commands.

SPL(FaultLoc+AllRepair)₁

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -domain polyhedra benchmarks/intro.c
Note: the option “-repair” means that we run an SPL repair algorithm after
SPLFaultLoc to repair the buggy SPL.
$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -domain polyhedra benchmarks/intro-b.c
$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -domain polyhedra benchmarks/cond.c
$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -domain polyhedra benchmarks/cond-b.c
$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -domain polyhedra benchmarks/while.c
$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -domain polyhedra benchmarks/easy2-1.c
$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -domain polyhedra benchmarks/Mysore-1.c
```

SPLAllRepair₁

```
$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/intro.c  
-m 1 -u 5 --argcomps n 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh
```

Note: the option “-m 1” means that we use mutations of level 1; the option “-u 5” represents the unwinding bound of the loops; the option “-argcomps n” means that in the mutation rules we use the argument “n”; “2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh” means that we use the script `ParseResults.sh` to automatically parse the output of the `SPLAllRepair` tool (output of the script are two files: a csv file with results summarized in a table and a text file with all found repairs, which can be found in the folder “RepairResults”).

```
$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/intro-b.c  
-m 1 -u 5 --argcomps n 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh
```

```
$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/cond.c  
-m 1 -u 5 --argcomps n 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh
```

```
$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/cond-b.c  
-m 1 -u 5 --argcomps n 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh
```

```
$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/while.c  
-m 1 -u 5 --argcomps n 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh
```

```
$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/easy2-1.c  
-m 1 -u 7 -s 6 --argcomps n 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh
```

```
$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/Mysore-1.c  
-m 1 -u 5 --argcomps x 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh
```

SPL(FaultLoc+AllRepair)₂

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -mut 2 -domain polyhedra benchmarks/intro.c
```

Note: the option “-mut 2” means that we apply mutations of level 2.

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -mut 2 -domain polyhedra benchmarks/intro-b.c
```

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -mut 2 -domain polyhedra benchmarks/cond.c
```

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -domain polyhedra benchmarks/cond-b.c
```

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -mut 2 -domain polyhedra benchmarks/while.c
```

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -mut 2 -domain polyhedra benchmarks/easy2-1.c
```

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -mut 2 -domain polyhedra benchmarks/Mysore-1.c
```

SPLAllRepair₂

```
$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/intro.c
-m 2 -u 5 --argcomps n 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh

$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/intro-b.c
-m 2 -u 5 --argcomps n 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh

$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/cond.c
-m 2 -u 5 --argcomps n 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh

$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/cond-b.c
-m 2 -u 5 --argcomps n 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh

$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/while.c
-m 2 -u 5 -s 5 --argcomps n 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh

$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/easy2-1.c
-m 2 -u 7 -s 5 --argcomps n 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh

$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/Mysore-1.c
-m 2 -u 5 -s 5 --argcomps x 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh
```

4 Experimental Results

Experiments are run on 64-bit Intel®Core™ i7-1165G7 CPU@2.80GHz, VM Xubuntu 22.04.3 LTS, with 8 GB memory, and we use a timeout value of 800 seconds. All times are reported as average over five independent executions. We report total running times, measured via `real` values of the `time` command, needed for the tasks to be performed.

4.1 Table 1

Table 1 shows the result of running: (1) our tool `SPLFaultLoc`, (2) the single backward analysis `SPLFaultLoc_Single`, and (3) the `Brute-force` approach on the given benchmarks. The column “`LOC`” is the total number of locations in the program, “`Time`” shows the run-time in seconds, “`RLOC`” is the number of potential relevant fault locations, and “`Prec`” is the precision (in percentage) of the given approach to locate the relevant statements for the error. This is the ratio of the sum of *correctly* classified relevant/irrelevant for the error locations by an approach to the total number of locations in the program. A classification of a location as relevant/irrelevant for the error given by the concrete semantics is considered correct.

Table 1. Performance results of `SPLFaultLoc` vs. `SPLFaultLoc_Single` vs. `Brute-force`. All abstract analyses use the Polyhedra domain. All times in sec.

Bench.	LOC	\mathbb{K}	SPLFaultLoc			SPLFaultLoc_Single			Brute-force	
			Time	RLOC	Prec	Time	RLOC	Prec	Time	Prec
<code>intro</code>	13	8	0.260	8	100%	0.031	9	90%	0.357	100%
<code>intro-b</code>	13	8	0.245	4	100%	0.028	9	50%	0.317	100%
<code>cond</code>	13	2	0.231	11	100%	0.030	13	80%	0.191	100%
<code>cond-b</code>	13	2	0.516	12	100%	0.028	7	50%	0.546	100%
<code>while</code>	17	8	1.528	11	100%	0.033	12	92%	2.298	100%
<code>easy2-1</code>	23	4	5.617	16	100%	0.031	6	50%	9.64	100%
<code>Mysore-1</code>	17	4	0.144	10	100%	0.051	17	50%	0.183	100%

For step-by-step detailed examination of the obtained outputs for each benchmark follow:

`ExperimentalResultsTable1.txt`

In the following, we show the obtained outputs of all three approaches on the example “`intro.c`”.

SPLFaultLoc

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -domain polyhedra benchmarks/intro.c
```

Abstract Syntax:	Error Invariant Map
[1:]	in 2nd Iteration
void main(int n){	[1:] A Bool && top
[2:] int z := n + 1;	[2:] A Bool && top
[3:] int y := n - 1;	[3:] A Bool && -n + z == 1
[4:] #if (A)	[4:] A Bool && -n + z == 1
[5:] y := z;	[5:] A Bool && -n + z == 1
[6:] #else	[6:] A Bool && -n + y == 1
[7:] #endif	[7:] bottom
[8:] #if (B&&C)	[8:] A Bool && -n + y == 1
[9:] z := z+1;	[9:] A and not B and CBool && -n + y == 1
[10:] #else	[10:] A and not B and CBool && -n + y == 1
[11:] #endif	[11:] A and not B and not C or A and B Bool && -n + y == 1
[12:] assert (y < n);	[12:] A Bool && -n + y == 1
[13:]	[13:] bottom

Abstract Syntax of Program Slice

```
[1:]
void main(int n){
[2:] #if (A)
    int z := n + 1;
    #endif
    Remove[3:]
[4:] #if (A)
[5:] y := z;
[6:] #else
[7:] #endif
    Remove[8:]
[12:] assert (y < n);
[13:]
```

Total time is: real 0m0,260s. There are 13 LOC in total. There are 8 LOC relevant for the bug: [1:], [2:], [4:], [5:], [6:], [7:], [12:], [13:], so we have 100% precision. This means that the statements in loc. [3:], [8:], [9], [10], [11:] are irrelevant for the error (5 LOC in total are irrelevant for the bug). The output log between "Abstract Syntax" of the input program and "Abstract Syntax of Program Slice" shows the results of backward and forward abstract analyses as well as the calculated Error Invariants for the input program. Their meaning is explained in the paper. Please see 'Motivating Examples' Section in the paper for detailed explanation of intro.c. For example, the error invariant at loc. [3:] is $A \text{ Bool} \mid \&\& -n + z == 1$, which means $(A \wedge -n + z = 1) \vee (\neg A \wedge \perp)$. Since the error invariants at locs. [3:] and [4:] are the same, the statement at loc [3:] is removed from the resulting program slice since it is irrelevant for the bug.

SPLFaultLoc_Single

```
$ time ./Main.native -single -domain polyhedra benchmarks/intro.c
```

Error Invariant Map
in 2nd Iteration

```
[13:] true Bool | && top
[12:] true Bool | && -n + y ≥ 0
[11:] true Bool | && -n + y ≥ 0
[10:] true Bool | && -n + y ≥ 0
[9:] true Bool | && -n + y ≥ 0
[8:] true Bool | && -n + y ≥ 0
[7:] true Bool | && -n + y ≥ 0
[6:] true Bool | && -n + y ≥ 0
[5:] true Bool | && -n + z ≥ 0
[4:] not A Bool | && -n + y ≥ 0 ||
      A Bool | && -n + z ≥ 0
[3:] A Bool | && -n + z ≥ 0
[2:] A Bool | && top
[1:] A Bool | && top
```

Abstract Syntax of
Program Slice

```
[1:]
void main(int n){
[2:] #if (A)
      int z := n + 1;
      #endif
[3:] int y := n - 1;
[4:] #if (A)
[5:] y := z;
[6:] #else
[7:] #endif
Remove[8:]
[12:] assert (y < n);
[13:]
```

Total time is: real 0m0,031s. There are 13 LOC in total. There are 9 LOC relevant for the bug: [1:], [2:], [3:], [4:], [5:], [6:], [7:], [12:], [13:], and the statements in loc. [8:], [9], [10], [11:] are irrelevant for the error (4 LOC in total are irrelevant for the bug). We do not count locations [1:] (before method definition), [12:] (the assertion definition), and [13:] (final location) in all benchmarks, since those locations are neither relevant nor irrelevant for the error. Hence, out of 10 meaningful locations, 5 are relevant and 5 are irrelevant for the bug in SPLFaultLoc. In SPLFault_Single, 5 relevant and 4 irrelevant locations are correctly classified, but 1 statement at [3:] is wrongly identified relevant. Therefore, the precision of SPLFault_Single is $9/10 = 90\%$.

Brute-Force

The eight variants of intro.c can be found in the folder benchmarks/intro.

```
$ time ./Main.native -bf -domain polyhedra benchmarks/intro
```

```
Analyze File: 0 benchmarks/intro/intro-3.c
```

Abstract Syntax of Program Slice

```
[1:]
void main(int n){
  Remove [2:]
  Remove [3:]
  Remove [4:]
[5:]
```

Variant intro-3.c is a correct program, so there are 0 LOC relevant for the bug.

Analyze File: 1 benchmarks/intro/intro-8.c
Abstract Syntax of Program Slice

```
[1 :]  
void main(int n){  
  Remove [2 :]  
  Remove [3 :]  
  Remove [4 :]  
[5 :]
```

Variant intro-8.c is a correct program, so there are 0 LOC relevant for the bug.

Analyze File: 2 benchmarks/intro/intro-4.c
Abstract Syntax of Program Slice

```
[1 :]  
void main(int n){  
  Remove [2 :]  
  Remove [3 :]  
  Remove [4 :]  
[5 :]
```

Variant intro-4.c is a correct program, so there are 0 LOC relevant for the bug.

Analyze File: 3 benchmarks/intro/intro-7.c
Abstract Syntax of Program Slice

```
[1 :]  
void main(int n){  
  Remove [2 :]  
  Remove [3 :]  
  Remove [4 :]  
[5 :]
```

Variant intro-7.c is a correct program, so there are 0 LOC relevant for the bug.

Analyze File: 4 benchmarks/intro/intro-2.c
Abstract Syntax of Program Slice

```
[1 :]  
void main(int n){  
[2 :] int z := n + 1;  
  Remove [3 :]  
[4 :] int y := z;  
  Remove [5 :]  
[6 :] assert(y < n);  
[7 :]
```

There are 2 LOCs irrelevant for the bug ([3:] and [5:]) in the variant intro-2.c.

Analyze File: 5 benchmarks/intro/intro-1.c
Abstract Syntax of Program Slice

```
[1:]  
void main(int n){  
[2:] int z := n + 1;  
  Remove [3:]  
[4:] int y := z;  
[5:] assert(y < n);  
[6:]
```

There is 1 LOC irrelevant for the bug ([3:]) in the variant intro-1.c.

Analyze File: 6 benchmarks/intro/intro-6.c
Abstract Syntax of Program Slice

```
[1:]  
void main(int n){  
[2:] int z := n + 1;  
[3:] int y := n - 1;  
[4:] int y := z;  
[5:] assert(y < n);  
[6:]
```

There is no irrelevant LOC for the bug in the variant intro-6.c.

Analyze File: 7 benchmarks/intro/intro-5.c
Abstract Syntax of Program Slice

```
[1:]  
void main(int n){  
[2:] int z := n + 1;  
[3:] int y := n - 1;  
[4:] int y := z;  
[5:] assert(y < n);  
[6:]
```

There is no irrelevant LOC for the bug in the variant intro-5.c.

Total time is: real 0m0,357s. The precision is 100%.

4.2 Table 2

Table 2 shows the performance of the approaches for repairing our benchmarks, that is, $\text{SPL}(\text{FaultLoc}+\text{AllRepair})_1$ and SPLAllRepair_1 with mutation level 1 as well as $\text{SPL}(\text{FaultLoc}+\text{AllRepair})_2$ and SPLAllRepair_2 with mutation level 2. The column **Space** is given as n/m where n is the explored and m is the total size of mutant search space, and **Time** is the running time in seconds.

For step-by-step detailed examination of the obtained outputs for each benchmark follow:

ExperimentalResultsTable2.txt

In the following, we show the obtained outputs of all four approaches on the example “intro.c”.

Table 2. Performance results of $SPL(\text{FaultLoc+AllRepair})$ vs. $SPL\text{AllRepair}$. All times in sec.

Bench.	$SPL(\text{FaultLoc+AllRepair})_1$		$SPL\text{AllRepair}_1$		$SPL(\text{FaultLoc+AllRepair})_2$		$SPL\text{AllRepair}_2$	
	Space	Time	Space	Time	Space	Time	Space	Time
intro	18/24	0.420	386/576	0.841	78/120	0.585	16206/27000	53.47
intro-b	8/12	0.464	196/576	0.575	22/30	0.517	12608/27000	50.61
cond	97/144	0.624	1729/2592	2.004	241/360	1.285	9006/19440	40.67
cond-b	335/432	1.205	1985/2592	2.620	2222/3240	8.348	13052/19440	71.02
while	96/96	2.470	2304/2304	11.42	1083/1920	10.60	?/230400	timeout
easy2-1	3093/73728	20.76	?/3538944	timeout	34766/12441600	764.8	?/8.9 × 10 ⁹	timeout
Mysore-1	5/6	0.409	769/1152	4.217	5/6	0.446	?/138240	timeout

Interpreting the output from $SPL\text{AllRepair}$ A possible repair is displayed like this:

```

-----
Possible Repair: ...
In file...
Replace...
with
...
In file...
Replace ..
with
...
-----

```

Which represents the patch you need to apply to the original program in order to repair it.

$SPL(\text{FaultLoc+AllRepair})_1$

\$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -domain polyhedra benchmarks/intro.c

Abstract Syntax
of Program Slice

```
[1:]  
void main(int n){  
[2:] #if (A)  
    int z := n + 1;  
    #endif  
Remove[3:]  
[4:] #if (A)  
[5:] y := z;  
[6:] #else  
[7:] #endif  
Remove[8:]  
[12:] assert(y < n);  
[13:]
```

```
-----  
Possible Repair: ...  
Elapsed time: 0.026 :  
In file temp.c line 8 function main:  
Replace z == n + 1 :  
with z == n - 1  
-----
```

```
-----  
Possible Repair: ...  
Elapsed time: 0.036 :  
In file temp.c line 8 function main:  
Replace z == n + 1 :  
with z == n - 2  
-----
```

```
Total space of mutants :  
- Program 18/24 :  
Done.  
real 0m0,420s
```

Total time is: real 0m0,420s. The Space of explored/total mutants is: 18/24. The above repairs suggest that the statement $z := n + 1$ at loc [2:] (or line 8 in temp.c) should be replaced with $z := n - 1$ or $z := n - 2$, to obtain the correct SPL.

SPLAllRepair₁

```
$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/intro.c  
-m 1 -u 5 --argcomps n 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh
```

The output of the ParseResults.sh script are two files: a csv file with results summarized in a table, and a text file with all found repairs and the elapsed time until each of them was found. The files can be found in a directory named RepairResults. We show the outputs in the text file.

```
-----  
Possible Repair: ...  
Elapsed time: 0.052 :  
In file benchmarks/intro0.c line 8 function main::  
Replace z == n + 1 :  
with z == n - 2  
-----
```

```
-----  
Possible Repair: ...  
Elapsed time: 0.055 :  
In file benchmarks/intro0.c line 8 function main:  
Replace z == n + 1 :  
with z == n - 1  
-----
```

STATISTICS:

file name = benchmarks/intro.c, max mutation size = 6, mutated programs = 576,
max inspected size = 6, smt check count = 386, found repairs = 2,
time to first repair [s] = 0.052, total time [s] = 0.841,

Total time is: 0.841s. The Space of explored/total mutants is smt check count/mutated
programs: 386/576. The above repair suggest that the statement $z := n + 1$ at
line 8 in intro.c should be replaced with $z := n - 2$ or $z := n - 1$, to obtain the
correct SPL.

SPL(FaultLoc+AllRepair)₂

\$ time ./Main.native -full -repair -mut 2 -domain polyhedra benchmarks/intro.c

```
-----  
Possible Repair: ...           Possible Repair: ...  
Elapsed time: 0.044 :         Elapsed time: 0.056 :  
In file temp.c line 8 f. main: In file temp.c line 8 f. main:  
Replace z == n + 1 :         Replace z == n + 1 :  
with z == SRem(n, 1)         with z == n * 0  
-----
```

```
-----  
Possible Repair: ...           Possible Repair: ...  
Elapsed time: 0.046 :         Elapsed time: 0.057 :  
In file temp.c line 8 f. main: In file temp.c line 8 f. main:  
Replace z == n + 1 :         Replace z == n + 1 :  
with z == n / 2              with z == n / 0  
-----
```

```
-----  
Possible Repair: ...           Possible Repair: ...  
Elapsed time: 0.054 :         Elapsed time: 0.067 :  
In file temp.c line 8 f. main: In file temp.c line 8 f. main:  
Replace z == n + 1 :         Replace z == n + 1 :  
with z == n - 1              with z == n - 2  
-----
```

```
Total space of mutants :
- Program 78/120 :
Done.
real 0m0,585s
```

Total time is: real 0m0,585s. The Space of explored/total mutants is: 78/120. The above repairs suggest that the statement $z := n + 1$ at loc [2:] (or line 8 in temp.c) should be replaced with $z := n\%1$, $z := n/2$, $z := n - 1$, $z := n * 0$ or $z := n - 2$..., to obtain the correct SPL.

SPLAllRepair₂

```
$ time bash -i AllRepair/scripts/SPLAllRepair.sh benchmarks/intro.c
-m 2 -u 5 --argcomps n 2>&1 | ./ParseResults.sh
```

```
-----
Possible Repair: ...           Possible Repair: ...
Elapsed time: 0.223 :         Elapsed time: 0.262 :
In file benchmarks/intro0.c line8 In file benchmarks/intro0.c line 8 :
Replace z == n + 1 :         Replace z == n + 1 :
with z == n-1)              with z == n / 2
-----
```

```
-----
Possible Repair: ...           Possible Repair: ...
Elapsed time: 0.247 :         Elapsed time: 0.275 :
In file benchmarks/intro0.c line8 In file benchmarks/intro0.c line 8 :
Replace z == n + 1 :         Replace z == n + 1 :
with z == n * 0             with z == n - 2
-----
```

```
-----
Possible Repair: ...           Possible Repair: ...
Elapsed time: 0.054 :         Elapsed time: 0.279 :
In file benchmarks/intro0.c line8 In file benchmarks/intro0.c line 8 :
Replace z == n + 1 :         Replace z == n + 1 :
with z == n / 0             with z == SRem(n, 1)
-----
```

STATISTICS:

```
file name = benchmarks/intro.c, max mutation size = 6, mutated programs = 27000,
max inspected size = 6, smt check count = 16206, found repairs = 6,
time to first repair [s] = 0.223, total time [s] = 53.478,
```

Total time is: 53.478s. The Space of explored/total mutants is smt check count/mutated programs: 16206/27000. The above repair suggest that the statement $z := n + 1$ at line 8 in intro.c should be replaced with $z := n - 1$, $z := n * 0$, $z := n/2$, or $z := n - 2$, $z := n\%1$, to obtain the correct SPL.

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